

ENHANCING THE OPPORTUNITIES OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FOR WOMEN THROUGH WEB 2.0 TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

Women education is the investment by any nation which gives best returns. Educated woman increases the opportunities of a good life for their families and especially for their children who consist the future generation. But in India we notice vast disparities among the education of two genders. This disparity is of two types, first there is a vast difference between the male and female education and second there is disparity among the female students of remote areas and big cities. We can also find some differences among the female students of different income levels. It is the need of hour to take some immediate and effective effort to make the education system more inclusive in terms of gender.

Since there is a wide spread of internet in India, it is advisable to connect the female students to the main stream education through web. In the last past decade a new version of web that is called web 2.0 has changed the way how people communicate. Present paper throws light on the use of web 2.0 technology to bring gender parity in the field of education.

Key words- Education, Gender Parity, Web 2.0, Inclusive Education.

INTRODUCTION

Education must ensure the right, to every individual to live with dignity and self-respect as a human being and play a constructive role in the society by developing a spirit which value, celebrate and respond to the diversity in the society. But the goal of education is achieved only when each and every member of the society has easy access to educational opportunities irrespective to their physical and social differences. Indian government is also committed for enhancing the educational opportunities to the larger sector of the community which is reflected in the constitutional provisions of “education for all” and universalization of education. These aims

need an inclusive system practice in education. Inclusion is an educational approach and philosophy that provides all students with community membership and greater opportunities for academic and social achievement. Inclusion is about making sure that each and every student feels welcome and that their unique needs and learning styles are attended to and valued. According to Nieto & Bode, "We want our classrooms to be just and caring, full of various conceptions of the good. We want them to be articulate, with the dialogue involving as many persons as possible, opening to one another, opening to the world". India is a country where the most neglected sector of the society is women in all the field of life. Since education is a way to ensure all round development to any one and complete success, it is must to give equal educational right to each woman. Internet can be a way to ensure proper inclusion of women in main educational system and gender parity.

The internet has revolutionized the concept of information and its use, access and management. "Today not only individuals and computers produce thousands of gigabytes of information in a minute, but this information is also networked collectively, which further increase the amount of information produced." As information grows and becomes more accessible, the concept of knowledge shifts too. Unlike Web 1.0, which was akin to a source or means of communicating information, Web 2.0 provides a way to create information, and consequently knowledge. Particularly in the last decade, the growth in prominence of social media and Web 2.0 technologies has had a dramatic impact globally on how people communicate. Today we are enveloped in a "cloud of ubiquitous digital information where knowledge is made, not found and authority is continuously negotiated through discussion and participation". Rather than just passively using the web to source information, Web 2.0 users are able to run rich internet applications in their browsers. Web 2.0 applications, such as blogs, wikis and aggregators, have a participative element, which encourages users to add, edit or simply rehash content. Web 2.0 allows learners to participate in this cloud, through five main characteristics, collaboration, creativity, conversation, community and control. It is

a read and write web where “users are as important as the content they upload and share with others”. The participatory and open nature of Web 2.0 gives us the capability to collaborate with new knowledge and to create empowering connections and community between people. It allows us to creatively use and reuse material in novel ways because there is not one centralized power controlling the web. Finally, and most importantly, Web 2.0 changes us from passive to active information consumers, allowing our online voice to be part of the conversation. The way we produce, store and consume information has changed, and we need Web 2.0 in order to interact with and to direct the future of scholarship and learning. That is why researcher tries to future scope to implement the new technology of ICT in the field of education by finding the level of awareness of web 2.0 tools among student teachers.

OBJECTIVES

- To discuss the role of Web 2.0 technology in enhancing the gender parity.
- To elaborate the different Web 2.0 applications which can be integrated in education system to enhance proper inclusion of females.
- To find out techniques of the Use of Web 2.0 Technology in Higher Education for Women Inclusion

METHODOLOGY

Content analysis method was used for this paper. Facts are collected through the analytical and evaluative study of literature available on the topic since 2008 both in online and offline mode.

How Web 2.0 Applications Enhance the opportunities of Inclusion

According to the final draft of RUSA (Rashtriya Uchchatar Shiksha Abhiyan) the enrollment rate of women in main stream education is less than 13%. So it is the demand for hour to incorporate the innovative ways in education system to increase the inclusion of

women. During the last years, many Web 2.0 technologies are adopted in various aspects of education. Under appropriate planning, Web 2.0 tools can be used with great success to support real educational activities and provide a very flexible and efficient form of inclusive education. By increasing access and equity through web 2.0 gender equality can be achieved in the field of education.

Access- India has a very low WER(Women Enrollment Ratio) of less than 13%, indicating that less than a fifth of the population in the age group of 18-23 years has access to higher education in India. It is even below than the BRICS countries. Higher education institutions receive only a limited pool of female students from the school education system.

On the other hand various surveys and reports tell that the India is the world largest country of internet access and 84% of total internet user use web 2.0 services. It can be easily understood that if the platform of online courses is developed and design it to support the various institutes' syllabus the access can be easily expanded. The researches could be undertaken to develop new Apps to support educational content by which education can reach in every hand through smart phones. This idea is slightly different from the online courses and availability of educational content on internet of distance learning institute. Researcher is talking about to develop a virtual educational society which is deliberately planned and carefully managed.

Equity- Inclusive education is a major goal of India to remove the disparities in educational system. The web 2.0 can also be helpful to ensure equity in the educational opportunities. Where the institutional access is low the education can be provided through online transmission of course. This is not like any static web pages which provide information or chapter wide material. It is not also the self instructional material available on web. There should be interactive sessions on web through live lectures, through videoconferencing or develop a portal like yahoo answers where students can post their questions and can get expert answers.

The females students coming from low economic status and from remote areas who are compel to drop out after school and cannot have access to higher education can have real classroom experience by this technology.

The Major Web 2.0 Technology Applications

Blogs - Blogs are user journal entries in the form of text, images, and links to web content, such as websites or other blogs. Blogs have a variety of formats and might include the user expressing their opinion about a topic or documenting activities. Blogs are interactive in the sense that other users could provide comments on the information posted by the blog author. Educational applications of blogs include researching, tracking, interpreting, and evaluating blogs for political commentary (multiple perspectives), cultural events, business, or other news and for examining changes over time.

Wikis - Wikis refer to collaborative websites that allow users to interact by adding, removing, or editing site content. The most well-known wiki implementation is Wikipedia. Wikipedia allows user to modify encyclopedic entries by creating a reviewer and editing structure. Wikipedia is shaped by the wisdom of the users and it is the richest source of information and terms especially for younger people . Wikis are useful in educational settings in that they support individualized learning, allowing for more socially defined search structures and promote collaboration through group editing and peer review.

Social networking - Social networks allow users to create personal profiles and establish a variety of networks that connect him/her with family, friends, and other colleagues. Currently, users utilize these sites to stay in touch with their friends, to make plans, make new friends. Extending this idea, these sites could be used to establish a series of academic connections or to foster cooperation and collaboration in the higher education classroom. Social book marking sites allow users to store, describe, and share numerous

web addresses with others. Users can explore bookmark collections of others by subscribing to their bookmark pages. If users are interested in a site they could tag it using few words to help others find it easily.

RSS

It is a technology which removes the need for the user to manually check the website for new content. Instead, their browser constantly monitors the site and informs the user of any updates. The browser can also be commanded to automatically download the new data for the user.

Techniques of the Use of Web 2.0 Technology in Higher Education for Women Inclusion

It is discussed above that the use of web 2.0 technologies can fulfill the need of nation of female education by ensuring equity, greater access and quality. Following are the ways which is suggested by the researcher on use of web 2.0 in the field of higher education:-

Virtual University- In India there are some institutions who established virtual classrooms and centers but they are not working towards the goal of greater access. The virtual classroom can be opened to the areas where the institutional density for females is low. A portal can be opened where students can attend the live lectures of the professors at the specified centers and post their queries on the web portal related to the universities and can get clarification.

Educational society- Social networking sites are very popular among us because they give us a feeling to have a discussion on every topic with our friends in our living room. Various educational social networking sites can be established where people with common interest and common needs can discuss and share their ideas related to the education. It can open the doors to collaboration and participation. It encourages and facilitates the natural desire to share what you know and to learn from your colleagues.

Interactive portal – A portal can be established where the opinions and comments related to educational world can be posted. Beside it various queries and doubts can be answered by the experts with clear citation. This portal can be common or can be related to certain university or college. There can be a regulatory board to arrange the haphazard content in a proper manner.

Innovation clusters- University Innovation Clusters should be set up in all geographical locations with the State University acting as a nodal point of such a cluster, with a view to building an innovation network with industry. These cluster centers can be incorporated with an interactive website where all the centers can collaborate their ideas.

Conclusion

The web 2.0 has the potential to reform the educational sector. It can make a radical revolution in the field of education. It is true that this need a lot of finance and regulatory work. There can be many barriers in full application of Web 2.0 technology in the field of education like uneasiness with openness, infrastructure, technical problems, time etc. But since various researches by government of India show that a large section of women population is far behind to their male counterparts and no one deny the importance of female education, it is highly needed to make it sure that every female student could avail the educational facilities. Since internet and smartphones are widely spread in India, Web 2.0 application can be an effective way to ensure female inclusion. It is suggested to government of India to take proper steps in this direction with the view of digital India.

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